

Impact of digital transformation on the strategic resilience and economic performance of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMES) in India: A multi-dimensional analysis

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Abstract

The Micro, small and medium enterprise (MSME) is an important sector in Indian economy contributing significantly in employment, industrial production as well as exports. The last few years have seen the rapid development of digital technologies that are significantly altering the conditions under which MSMEs operate, enabling companies to become more efficient and develop a broader array of markets while improving their resilience to economic shocks. By embracing a multi-dimensional analytical approach, the paper examines the effect of digital transformation on strategic resilience and economic performance of MSMEs in India.

The study also explores the contribution of digital technologies, including cloud computing, E-commerce, artificial intelligence, and electronic payment systems, in the development of MSMEs' productivity. The study is based on a mixed research method that will involve a systematic literature study, secondary data analysis based on government/industry reports, and data obtained through surveys carried out in MSMEs in India. The statistical analysis of data indicates that digital investment is significantly positively correlated with business turnover, indicating that digital transformation is very effective in enhancing financial performance.

The study concludes that digital transformation of MSMEs is effective in enhancing their growth in sales, growth in customers, and operational efficiency. However, some issues remain that can affect the full development of digital transformation, including low financing, digital literacy, and differential access to technology in rural areas. The study also emphasizes that government initiatives, including digital payment systems such as Unified Payment Interface (UPI), Government E-Marketplace (GeM), digital credit systems, are very important in helping MSMEs join the digital economy.

The study concludes that even though digital transformation is a major contributor to MSMEs' growth and development, specific support is required to ensure that digital transformation is inclusive and sustainable in MSMEs.

Keywords:

Digital Transformation, MSMEs, Digital Economy, Financial Inclusion, Technology Adoption, Economic Growth.